

Evaluation of dysphagia severity in patients with nasopharyngeal carcinoma undergoing radiotherapy

Rita Angela NICITA^{1*}, Parisa Jalilzadeh AFSHARI², Mahmood BAHRAMIZADEH³, Rezvaneh NAMAZI YOUSEFI⁴, Francesco CIODARO⁵

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¹Department of Adult and Developmental Human Pathology "Gaetano Barresi", University of Messina, Messina, Italy. E-mail: ritanicita@alice.it

²Department of Audiology, School of Rehabilitation Sciences, University of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Sciences, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: jalilzadeh.a.p@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-7644-2492

³Department of Orthotics and Prosthetics, School of Rehabilitation Sciences, University of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Sciences, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: mbzqandp@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0003-4719-938x

⁴Research Center, Deputy of Research and Technology, University of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Sciences, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: mrs.rezvanebnamazj@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-8013-2534

⁵Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine, University of Messina, Messina, Italy

*Correspondence

Abstract

Introduction: Dysphagia in patients treated with radiotherapy for Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma has limited empirical evidence. The aim of this study was to identify specific foods and feeding methods recommended for these patients and to evaluate the anatomical and functional structures most affected by radiotherapy doses.

Methods: Nine patients with Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma, previously treated with Radio- or Radio chemotherapy and not undergoing head and neck surgery, participated in the study. The patients had undergone either 3D Conformal Radiotherapy (3D-CRT) or Intensity-Modulated Radiotherapy (IMRT) and were evaluated using a questionnaire developed by Travalca Cupillo et al., (2011) an assessment form for adult dysphagic patients, followed by a Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (FEES).

Results: The study revealed motor deficits primarily in the initial phases of swallowing (oral phase and pharyngeal trigger), with borderline conditions that would have been missed by a screening questionnaire, as patients did not report specific symptoms. Symptoms were even less evident in patients who underwent IMRT instead of 3D-CRT, in patients who lost less weight during radiotherapy, in patients with N0 at diagnosis, and in younger patients.

Discussion and Conclusions: Patients treated with radiotherapy in the head and neck region present with various forms of dysphagia, sometimes silent. The use of proper oral hygiene and appropriate food consistencies can reduce the risk of pulmonary complications.

Take-home message: It is recommended to study the swallowing function in all patients undergoing radiotherapy in the head and neck region.

Keywords: Dysphagia; nasopharyngeal carcinoma; radiotherapy.

INTRODUCTION

Dysphagia, or difficulty in swallowing, is a common complication in patients undergoing radiotherapy for nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC). Despite its prevalence, empirical evidence specifically addressing dysphagia in this patient population remains limited. Dysphagia can significantly impact the quality of life, leading to malnutrition, dehydration, and aspiration pneumonia, thereby complicating the treatment and recovery process. This study aims to identify specific foods and feeding methods recommended for patients with NPC who have undergone radiotherapy and to evaluate the anatomical and functional structures most affected by radiotherapy doses.

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is a malignant tumor arising from the nasopharynx's epithelial cells. Due to its epidemiological, histological, and clinical characteristics, it is distinct from other head and neck cancers. Radiotherapy is a primary treatment modality for NPC due to the tumor's radiosensitivity and the anatomical complexity of the nasopharyngeal region, which limits surgical options [1].

Radiotherapy, while effectively targeting tumor cells, often results in collateral damage to the surrounding healthy tissues, including the muscles and nerves involved in the swallowing mechanism. This can lead to various degrees of dysphagia, with symptoms ranging from mild discomfort to severe difficulty in swallowing solids and liquids [2]. The severity and onset of dysphagia can vary, with some patients experiencing immediate effects during treatment while others develop symptoms months or years post-therapy [3].

The pathophysiology of radiotherapy-induced dysphagia involves several factors. Radiation can cause mucositis, fibrosis, and edema in the oropharyngeal and laryngeal regions, impairing muscle function and coordination necessary for effective swallowing [4]. Additionally, xerostomia (dry mouth) resulting from radiation damage to salivary glands further complicates the swallowing process by reducing saliva production, which is crucial for bolus formation and lubrication [5].

Empirical studies on dysphagia in NPC patients are sparse, with most research focusing on general head and neck cancer populations. These studies indicate that dysphagia management should be individualized, considering the specific anatomical and functional deficits caused by radiotherapy. Commonly recommended interventions include dietary modifications, swallowing exercises, and using compensatory strategies to facilitate safer swallowing [6]. However, specific guidelines tailored to NPC patients still need to be developed, highlighting the need for further research.

Aim of the study

The present study addresses the gap in empirical evidence by focusing on dysphagia in NPC patients treated with radiotherapy. Identifying specific foods and feeding methods and evaluating the most affected anatomical and functional structures, the findings aim to enhance dysphagia management in this unique patient population, ultimately improving their quality of life and treatment outcomes.

METHODS

Study design and population target

This observational study was conducted in Italy at the Otorhinolaryngology Unit of the G. Martino University Hospital in Messina. The patients were selected during the sessions of the Oncology Committee (comprising an Otorhinolaryngologist, Radiotherapist, Oncologist, Radiologist, and Maxillofacial Surgeon).

Sampling procedure and study instruments

During the sessions of the Oncology Committee (comprising an Otorhinolaryngologist, Radiotherapist, Oncologist, Radiologist, and Maxillofacial Surgeon), held at our Otorhinolaryngology clinics, we selected nine patients with the following characteristics: patients with Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma (regardless of TNM stage), previously treated with Radio- or Radiochemotherapy (at least three months post-treatment), who had not undergone head and neck surgery (except for biopsy for histological determination of the tumor) [7-9]. The patients observed had undergone either 3D Conformal Radiotherapy (3D-CRT) or Intensity-Modulated Radiotherapy (IMRT) and were studied using a questionnaire developed by Travalca Cupillo, Castellini, and Biondi (2011) [10], an assessment form for adult dysphagic patients, followed by a Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (FEES). The questionnaire used a scale from 0 to 3 with the following values: 0 = normal movement; 1 = slightly altered movement; 2 = highly altered movement; 3 = absent movement. Each patient signed an informed consent form (based on the model proposed by the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association in 2003, as reiterated by Nacci et al. in 2008) [11]. Patients were thoroughly informed about the nature of the exam to increase their compliance with the video endoscopy, explaining the exact procedure and considering their expectations regarding the exam results.

The FEES methodology standardized for these patients was modified from the widely described approach in the literature and used in various ENT centers focusing on swallowing. Our goal was to identify specific foods and feeding methods recommended for these patients and, more importantly, to evaluate the anatomical and functional structures most affected by radiotherapy doses. Therefore, we found it more relevant to monitor the consistencies that anecdotally caused more difficulty for the patient, not relying on predefined food types and quantities but preferring a comparative evaluation between foods we administered and those managed independently by the patient. Two professionals conducted the exam: the otorhinolaryngologist and the speech therapist.

The patients observed in our study had undergone either 3D Conformal Radiotherapy (3D-CRT) or Intensity-Modulated Radiotherapy (IMRT). They were evaluated using a questionnaire developed by Travalca, Cupillo, Castellini, and Biondi, an assessment form for adult dysphagic patients, followed by a Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (FEES), which demonstrated good validity and reliability [10]. The questionnaire we used employed a rating scale from 0 to 3 with the following values: 0 = normal movement; 1 = slightly altered movement; 2 = highly altered movement; 3 = absent movement.

Furthermore, the Penetration-Aspiration Scale was employed. Its scores range from 1 to 8:

Score 1: No penetration or aspiration; material does not enter the airway.

Score 2-5: Various degrees of penetration without aspiration. For example, a score of 2 might indicate that material enters the airway but remains above the vocal cords and is cleared spontaneously.

Score 6-8: Various degrees of aspiration. A score of 8 indicates silent aspiration, where material passes below the vocal cords without any cough reflex to clear it.

Specific cut-off scores are established to help clinicians make decisions regarding patient care. For example, a penetration-aspiration score of 5 or higher may indicate an increased risk of aspiration, suggesting the need for dietary modifications or swallowing therapy. Residue scores of 3 or 4 might indicate the need for strategies to improve bolus clearance or reduce residue, such as changes in posture, swallow maneuvers, or texture modifications.

Each patient signed an informed consent form about the procedure and its risk (based on the model proposed by the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association in 2003, reiterated by Nacci et al. in 2008) [11].

The FEES methodology standardized for these patients was slightly modified from the widely described approach in the literature and used in various ENT centers focusing on swallowing [10-12]. Our goal was to identify specific foods and feeding methods recommended for these patients and evaluate the anatomical and functional structures most affected by radiotherapy doses. Therefore, we found it more relevant to monitor the consistencies that anecdotally caused more difficulty for the patient, not relying on predefined food types and quantities but preferring a comparative evaluation between foods we administered and those managed independently by the patient. Two professionals carried out the assessment: the otorhinolaryngologist and the speech therapist.

Table 1. Lips in movement: percentage of patients by type and degree of deficit.

Ethical aspects

This study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards, with approval from the Local Ethics Committee. All participants provided informed consent after being thoroughly briefed on the study's nature, procedures, and potential risks. The study ensured patient confidentiality, adhered to ethical regulations, and allowed participants to withdraw without affecting their ongoing treatment. To increase their compliance with the video endoscopy, patients were thoroughly informed about the nature of the examination, explained the exact procedure and its risk, and always considered their expectations regarding the exam results (Table 1).

RESULTS

In the anamnesis, special consideration was given to the original tumor site (more on the right or left), the positive lymph nodes and their location (if present), the type of radiotherapy, the parameters of dose and volumes administered, and any associated chemotherapy. The patients' descriptions of their dysphagia symptoms (subjective symptoms: dry mouth, difficulty swallowing dry or spicy foods, coughing after drinking liquids, etc.) were carefully evaluated. They also highlighted the compensatory strategies they used to manage these foods (such as water, oil, or wrapping dry foods in viscous foods). Most patients reported difficulty swallowing solid or semi-solid, dry foods. Liquid dysphagia was described as intermittent post-swallow coughing or after consuming carbonated liquids. All patients clearly described a sensation of "food stuck in the upper throat" behind the tongue and, less frequently, a sensation of "food stuck in the lower throat," necessitating

frequent throat clearing. Xerostomia is a significant post-radiotherapy symptom, even a year after treatment. In the absence of comorbidities, in younger patients, especially those who underwent IMRT instead of 3D-CRT, subjective symptoms were significantly lower compared to other patients. Another important aspect in the evaluation of swallowing was the anamnesis-reported "food coming out of the nose," which, upon close analysis, indicated a more significant palatal motor deficit in these patients. All patients who underwent radiotherapy lost weight immediately post-treatment, partially or entirely regaining it (only in two out of nine cases) over the years. All patients reported a deterioration in quality of life, mainly due to changes in diet (both qualitatively and quantitatively). Literature analysis revealed that this aspect had been the subject of various studies, which also considered the emotional solid component, performing screenings with self-assessment questionnaires [6].

Three functions were analyzed and found to have deficits: controlling breathing, phonation, and saliva dispersion. Morphological and functional examinations of the oro-pharynx-laryngeal structures were then conducted, evaluating the various districts' anatomy and functionality. In this initial phase, the following were considered: motor and sensory deficits, asymmetry (atrophy, edema), and salivary residues.

Upon careful evaluation, a (mild-moderate) deviation of the buccal rim was unexpectedly noted towards the more irradiated side, associated with atrophy and contracture phenomena. We observed asthenia and deficits in lip movement, especially concerning opening, protrusion, and coordination of the motor act (orbicularis oris muscle, mentalis muscle, chin's droplet, and levator labii superioris). This finding was somewhat unusual, as the literature primarily analyzes swallowing in radio-treated patients in the head and neck area, focusing mainly on the pharyngolaryngeal phase. In contrast, this study found that radiotherapy can also significantly alter the oral phase.

The tongue exhibited morphological-structural alterations at rest, impacting motor deficits. Tongue movement showed deficits primarily in protrusion and elevation-lowering movements, with evident motor incoordination. The intrinsic muscles of the tongue (anterior to the V linguale) and the extrinsic muscles (hyoglossus and genioglossus, responsible for tongue depression and protrusion, respectively) were involved, all playing a role in the initial phase of bolus preparation. Additionally, deficits in the styloglossus muscle, which retracts and elevates the posterior part of the tongue along with the posterior intrinsic muscles, were observed, affecting the subsequent phase of moving the bolus into the oropharynx and triggering the pharyngeal reflex. Similar considerations can be made, with appropriate adjustments, for the jaw, which also appeared to have deviated in a smaller percentage of cases.

The mandibular opening movement was variably limited, depending on the time elapsed since the last RT cycle and the patient's compliance with chewing exercises typically recommended by the radiotherapist. The deficit persisted even in patients who consistently exercised, significantly limiting mandibular excursion during chewing and bolus preparation. The most affected muscles were the mylohyoid, digastric, geniohyoid, and stylohyoid muscles (involved in mandibular depression and concurrent elevation of the tongue base and hyoid bone). Conversely, there was a higher percentage of slippage (and thus alteration in movement fluidity) due to deficits in the masticatory muscles (masseter, medial and lateral pterygoid, temporalis), predominantly on the irradiated side. However, oral hygiene, occlusion, and dental status were also important considerations.

The presence or absence of teeth was highly significant, as many studies have shown an inverse relationship between better oral hygiene and the likelihood of lower respiratory tract infections post-radiotherapy. Better dental conditions seemed to reduce the risk of aspiration pneumonia after radiotherapy, regardless of the dose received. Comorbidities and persistent smoking habits were also predictive of pneumonia, suggesting that aspiration alone is not a sufficient cause of pneumonia. This is crucial as it explains why some patients with silent aspiration did not experience significant febrile episodes attributable to lower respiratory tract inflammation, which was carefully considered in the conclusions and recommendations provided in their reports. Additionally, in this study, the presence or absence of teeth (corrected or not) allowed for consideration of potential motor incoordination important for the final evaluation.

In the anamnesis, it emerged that patients who had undergone total or near-total tooth extractions during dental clearance before radiotherapy and who, despite needing them, did not use dentures due to post-radiation stomatitis altered the precarious balance of the masticatory system. This heavily impacted nutritional intake in the initial phases and facilitated states of malnutrition, affecting muscle trophic status and compounding the effects of radiation damage. The soft palate was extremely affected by the outcomes of radiotherapy.

Palatal and swallowing function assessment

Both asymmetries at rest and during phonation were evident. Additionally, there was observable stiffness with a reduced range of motion; the strength and tension over time were inadequate in most of the patients examined (Table 2).

Table 2. Tongue Movement Deficit. Percentage of patients by type and degree of deficit.

Endoscopic examination with different food consistencies

The next phase of the examination involved using a flexible endoscope. We administered four types of foods to our patients: water colored with methylene blue for liquids; aquagel for semi-liquids; a solution composed of water, methylene blue, and thickener (with a very thick consistency) for semi-solids; and dry biscuits for solids.

We first conducted an objective anatomical-functional evaluation, followed by an analysis of salivary residues. Then we provided patients with portions of each food decided by us and finally asked the patients to self-administer the portions. This final step had a clear clinical significance to evaluate any faults in food self-management, useful for enriching therapeutic advice and potentially setting up speech therapy treatment if needed.

Figure 1. Experimental material.

Evaluation scale and analysis

For each consistency, the same rating scale (0, 1, 2, 3) was used, assigning a numerical value corresponding to the degree of deficit within the different swallowing phases. This yielded an analysis of the individual muscle components related to the various phases. Initially, patients were guided through the evaluation, educating them to hold water in their mouth and release it on command to check containment capacity and, particularly for solids, to chew thoroughly and swallow upon request. In a subsequent phase, patients were allowed to autonomously decide the quantities and timing of food management. This enabled us to differentiate premature food drops caused by muscle deficits from those due to hasty or poor food

management by the patients. The muscular deficit identified in the anatomical-functional analysis of the oro-pharynx-laryngeal structures was confirmed during the swallowing test, with the most significant alterations observed in the propulsive oral phase, initiation of the pharyngeal reflex, and apnea-swallowing coordination. The propulsive movement of the extrinsic and intrinsic tongue muscles appeared altered both qualitatively and quantitatively (reduced contraction maintenance time).

Sensitivity evaluation

An important consideration before evaluating the various swallowing phases is the “sensitivity” of the analyzed structures. Although we did not have the equipment for FEEST, which uses regulated air pressures, we could assess the subjects' sensitivity by simply touching the various structures with the endoscope tip or, where possible, with a tongue depressor. A considerable percentage of patients showed variable degrees of sensitivity alteration.

Functional deficits and clinical findings

It is evident from Figure 2 that a significant percentage of patients had a sensitivity deficit. In patients with severe palatal involvement, there was a noticeable inability to contain food, with premature droppage without pre-swallow coughing. An initial extraoral evaluation often revealed slight atrophy of the buccinator muscle, which narrows the vestibule, retracts the cheeks and keeps the bolus between the molars during chewing. The sensory alteration of the tongue is crucial in managing the intraoral bolus, with greater desensitization noted on the side that received a more intense treatment dose. Patients reported dysgeusia and ageusia during radiotherapy and a reversal of sweet-salty taste.

Nasal regurgitation and pharyngeal sensitivity

Patients with altered sensitivity of the posterior pharyngeal wall often also had altered laryngeal sensitivity (standardized by sequentially testing the epiglottis, aryepiglottic folds, piriform sinuses, and arytenoids). The altered sensitivity of the glottic plane is an essential rehabilitative parameter as it limits the possibility of speech therapy treatment. Laryngeal penetration was frequent, particularly with solids; it was hypothesized that reduced action of the intrinsic and extrinsic tongue muscles contributed to less fluid movement of the epiglottis. This led to food residues in the valleculae, the epiglottis, and the piriform sinuses. Patients reported subjective symptoms of "food stuck in the upper throat."

Residuals and nasal regurgitation

Food residues were mainly solids and semi-solids, located bilaterally in the piriform sinuses and valleculae. Differences between the two sides were especially notable with liquids, with more significant residues on the more irradiated side. In a few cases, residue persisted on the upper surface of the vocal cords, with aspiration observed in only one case (a patient with a previous stroke).

Two patients exhibited nasal regurgitation during endoscopy; three patients reported sporadic episodes of food coming out of the nose (mainly liquids, but also small solid foods like legumes) during or immediately after treatment in the anamnesis.

Clinical implications

Given this analysis, it is justified to consider a compromise of the palatoglossus muscle (which elevates the posterior part of the tongue, lowers the soft palate, and closes the oral cavity, participating in the oral phase) and the pharyngostaphylinus muscle. Considering patients with nasal regurgitation, deficits in the uvular muscle (which raises the uvula), the internal peripharyngeal muscle (levator veli palatini), and the external peripharyngeal muscle (tensor veli palatini) are evident. The superior pharyngeal constrictor muscle (notable in liquid dysphagia) and the middle and inferior constrictors (facilitating bolus progression and whose deficits mainly cause solid food dysphagia) are also involved. Clinically, it was useful to employ evaluation parameters such as the Penetration-Aspiration Scale:

1. No material enters the airway.
2. Material enters the airway but does not reach the vocal cords and is completely expelled.
3. Material enters the airway, does not reach the vocal cords, but is not completely expelled.
4. Material enters the airway, touches the vocal cords, but is completely expelled.
5. Material enters the airway and touches the vocal cords but is not completely expelled.
6. Material enters the airway, passes below the vocal cords, but is completely expelled.
7. Material enters the airway, passes below the vocal cords, and is not expelled, but the patient attempts to expel it (coughing).
8. Material enters the airway, passes below the vocal cords, is not expelled, and there is no attempt to expel it.

Figure 2. Movement deficit
 Movement Deficit

Overall, this comprehensive examination of dysphagia in patients' post-radiotherapy for nasopharyngeal carcinoma reveals significant functional deficits across various anatomical structures involved in swallowing. These findings underscore the necessity for tailored therapeutic interventions and continuous monitoring to manage dysphagia effectively and improve patient outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This study originated from the opportunity provided by the Multidisciplinary Oncology Committee of the Head and Neck District to compare the expertise of each specialist, express doubts, and evaluate the diagnostic-therapeutic possibilities and cross-sectional research potential of each involved medical sector. This collaboration made the need to assess swallowing emerge in patients with nasopharyngeal carcinoma who underwent radiotherapy or radiochemotherapy.

While the use of self-assessment questionnaires is widespread in the literature, this study instead utilized the collaboration between the otolaryngologist and the speech therapist for the monofunctional evaluation and employed the FEES method, which is currently considered the gold standard among swallowing examinations due to its diagnostic validity, reduced invasiveness (compared to video fluoroscopy, which is still a radiological exam), and ability to evaluate all supraesophageal phases of swallowing, residues, and anatomy. This method is a simple, straightforward, low-cost endoscopic evaluation system that is especially repeatable over time, which could allow for increasing experience and enrichment for both the specialist and the patient [12-15].

From this study, motor deficits emerged primarily in the early phases of swallowing (oral phase and pharyngeal trigger initiation), with borderline cases that a screening questionnaire would have missed, as patients did not report specific symptoms. Symptoms were less evident in patients who underwent IMRT instead of 3D-CRT, in patients who lost less weight during radiotherapy, in patients with N0 at diagnosis, and in younger patients. The only exception was a young subject who did not follow the physiological swallowing patterns in the oral phase, initiation (accelerated), and pharyngeal phase due to self-control deficits with lingual-buccal-facial praxis incoordination [16-19].

Consistent with the literature, we observed that the presence or absence of teeth has a determining value in achieving better masticatory function; additionally, good oral hygiene seems to have a positive prognostic value in protecting the lower airways. Under equal general conditions, among two subjects presenting an aspiration, the one with better oral hygiene is less likely to develop a lower airway infection [20-24]. We described sensory deficits, particularly at the soft palate and pharynx levels, which significantly contribute to the altered management of the oral and pharyngeal phases in patients with already compromised muscle control. Finally, we provided practical dietary advice for these patients (instead of the simple classic prescription of products like artificial saliva), a method for home monitoring at-risk patients referred for speech therapy treatment.

Study limitations

This study is limited by its small sample size, which restricts the generalizability of the findings. The observational design cannot establish causal relationships, and the absence of a control group limits comparisons. Additionally, reliance on a specific questionnaire and FEES protocol may not capture all aspects of dysphagia, and variability in patient compliance with post-radiotherapy care could have influenced the results. Future research with larger, randomized samples and diverse assessment tools is needed to validate these findings.

CONCLUSIONS

The study confirms that patients treated with radiotherapy in the head and neck region present with various, sometimes silent, dysphagia patterns. Dysphagia, or difficulty swallowing, can significantly impact a patient's quality of life and overall health, often leading to complications such as malnutrition, dehydration, and aspiration pneumonia [20-24].

Patients may not always be aware of their swallowing difficulties, making it crucial for healthcare providers to conduct thorough evaluations. Methods like FEES can identify subtle deficits that self-assessment questionnaires might miss. Targeted interventions can be implemented by understanding these patients' specific swallowing challenges.

Proper oral hygiene [25] and appropriate food consistencies [16] can play a critical role in reducing the risk of pulmonary complications. Maintaining good oral hygiene helps prevent infections, while modifying food textures can help manage dysphagia more effectively, reducing the likelihood of aspiration and subsequent respiratory issues.

It is recommended that swallowing function be studied in all patients undergoing radiotherapy in the head and neck region. Regular monitoring and early intervention can help manage symptoms better, improve patient outcomes, and enhance the quality of life for these individuals [26,27]. Integrating multidisciplinary approaches involving otolaryngologists, speech therapists, and dietitians is essential in providing comprehensive care and support to patients with nasopharyngeal carcinoma undergoing radiotherapy.

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